

LEARNING ACTIVITIES AND MOTIVATION IN PRESCHOOL AND JUNIOR SCHOOL AGE

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the problem of educational motivation and its management in the educational process, as well as the relevance and importance of the topic, are explained in detail, the goals and tasks are described, and the practical significance is presented.

When a person performs some activity during his life, the activity its effectiveness depends on a person's desire, desire or desire for this activity. In this place, the question of motivation becomes important. In a broad sense, motivation is considered a complex multifaceted manager of human life (behavior, activity).

Motivation is a complex, multi-level system of encouraging a person to act.

it embodies needs, motives, interests, ideals, aspirations, norms, emotions, norms, values.

Motivation is a complex structure, a set of forces driving activity, which manifests itself in the form of inclinations and ideals and directly determines and controls human activity. Motivation is a set of reasons that encourage a person to be active. Different expressions of the concept of motivation, a certain question about the content and energetic aspect of motivation have been expressed by psychologists. For foreign psychologists, the concept of motivation is considered as a source of characteristic specific one-sided energy activity, they allocate energy and behavior as concrete mechanisms, ignoring the content side.

The problem of motive and motivation is a different point of view in world psychology

is being researched through a conceptual approach. In far and near foreign countries, specific psychological schools have emerged, in their view, scientific positions and concepts embody ideas and trends that differ in essence. Representatives of Russian psychology K. D. Ushinsky, I. M. Sechenov, I. P. Pavlov, V. M. Bekhterev, A. F. Lazurisky, V. N. Myasishev, A. A. Ukhtomisky, D. N. Uznadze, S. L. Rubinshtein, A. N. Leontev, P. M. Yakobson, L. I. Bojovich and others conducted research on this problem. In addition to representatives of Russian psychology, there are more than thirty scientific concepts of motivation in European and American countries. We will try to reflect on the research of some manifestations of these psychological schools: introspective psychology, behaviorism, Gestalt psychology, psychoanalysis, structural psychology, associationist psychology, empirical psychology, analytical psychology, humanistic psychology, anthropological psychology, etc.

According to psychological data, any activity arises under the influence of certain motives and takes place only when sufficient conditions are created. Therefore, in order to ensure mastery, acquisition and implementation of learning in the educational process, it is necessary for students to have learning motives. Motives of knowledge are directed towards the epistemological goal of the person (subject), that is, to decide on the goal of knowledge, to acquire knowledge and skills. Usually, according to theoretical information, such similar and same-sex motifs are called external and internal names and create a certain category. External motives arise under the influence of stimuli such as punishment and reward, danger and demand, group pressure, good intentions, and desires.

All these are external factors and causes directly related to the educational goal. In this case, knowledge and skills serve to ensure the realization of other, dominant (leading) goals that are more important (avoiding unpleasant situations and experiences or unpleasant, uncomfortable situations, achieving social or personal success; the existence of a temporary scope of achievement, etc.) . Under the influence of external motives of this type or gender, difficulties arise in the acquisition (mastery) of knowledge and skills in the educational process, and they prevent the realization of the main goal. For example, the primary goal of elementary school students is not to study, but to play more. In this situation, the teacher's intention to involve them in learning can destroy the achievement of the goal of the game, but there is a lack of evidence. The next category of motives, i.e., the group of internal motives, includes motives of individual characteristics, which appear in the student's personality on the basis of the motivation to realize the individual goal in relation to studying. For example, the emergence of interest in knowledge is the fulfillment of the aspirations of a person to increase his spiritual (cultural) level.

Under the influence of similar motives, conflicting situations (situations) do not arise in the educational process. Of course, despite the emergence of motives related to such a category, sometimes difficulties may arise, because it is necessary to make a willful effort to acquire knowledge. Voluntary efforts with such properties are aimed at reducing the power and capacity of external destructive motivators (instigators). When approaching this process from the point of view of pedagogical psychology, only the perfect situation is called optimal (reasonable). Creating such situations in the educational process is considered an important task of the teacher, and his activities are not limited to controlling the behavior of students, but also to forming their personality, being able to set goals, arouse interest and ideals in them. will be aimed at finding content. Motivation is the processes that determine the movement towards the goal, the factors influencing the activity or passivity of this behavior. The main link of motivation is motivation - a behavioral manifestation of satisfying one's own needs. American psychologist A. Maslov's positive holistic-dynamic theory of motivation defines five basic needs:

Physiological needs - they are related to the satisfaction of food, water, sexual needs.

The need for security - the need for safety, stability, protection, structure and order;

The need for love - it includes the desire to communicate, belonging to a social group self respect.

The need for self-actualization is the individual's desire for self-realization, actualization of his potential. Then, behind the proposed five-level needs model, Maslow has two more needs: the need for knowledge and understanding and aesthetic needs. The need

for knowledge and understanding are cognitive needs of humans. It is related to the need for truth, the attraction of the unknown, the incomprehensible. This need is closely related to learning motivation. Aesthetic needs are characterized by more fragmentation and uncertainty. They are closely related to conative and cognitive needs. Motives can be characterized not only quantitatively (according to the strong-weak principle), but also qualitatively. In this regard, internal and external motives are usually distinguished. At the same time, it is possible to talk about the attitude of the motive to the content of the activity.

Example: We can distinguish the identity of the cognitive need - the need to learn. Then we talk about intrinsic motivation. If education is related to the need to increase social prestige, salary, then it is necessary to talk about external motives. In addition, external motives themselves can be positive (success, success motives) and negative (avoidance, protection motives). It can be seen that extrinsic positive motives are more effective than extrinsic negative motives even if they are equal in strength. External positive motives effectively affect the academic results of educational activities.

When studying the characteristics of educational motivation, it is necessary to distinguish 2 aspects:

The first aspect is the motivation for choosing educational activities. The second is to determine the reason why the scientist decided to study this topic. Doing science depends on several reasons. They need to strive for new things and create them, to be interested in specific sciences and to be interested in some specific issues, to benefit humanity with their discoveries, to solve any issues related to the national economy, or simply to make a name for themselves in history with their work. leave; the pursuit of a certain social status (having academic degrees) is defined by the pursuit of fame.

It is an important part of pedagogical activity and is seen in its motivation. Pedagogical activities are divided into motivational orientations, as in educational activities.

They are external motives, for example orientation to the result and process of one's activity. The external motives of work prestige in a specific educational institution, the motives of adequacy of remuneration for labor, are often closely related to the motives of professional and personal growth.

G. A. Murray separates the main motives of striving for power, connecting them with their activities. The signs or effects of need are manifested in the following desires: 1. Management of one's social world; 2. To influence the behavior of others and guide them with their advice, command, convince them of their word; 3. Orientation to one's faith. All factors of motivation can be divided into tangible and intangible incentives. "Life is not just eating and drinking." In other words, attracting employees with money is not enough. In addition to material incentives, an additional, non-material system of motivating employees may be developed in the enterprise. It should be designed to fulfill their important needs from psychological and economic aspects. The implementation of the principle is determined by the development of positive motivations aimed at encouraging high-performing employees. Reflects the "Negative Motivations" inherent in the system of punishments for low-income workers.

Which of the motives predominates, positive or negative? the answer to the question can be solved depending on the process of working in a specific enterprise and establishing a relationship with employees.

Therefore, the motivation should be adequate and match the work results of the employee of the enterprise. The motivation system will not be effective if there is punishment for mistakes, life, work results and irregularities. In addition, external factors of motivation that teach employees to evaluate their own results and internal motivational factors related to the level of success of the company's employees can also be distinguished.

If the evaluation of the leader forms the assessment of the results of the leaders, this is a good indicator. In this case, the manager's assessment from the outside and the employees' self-assessment are consistent. V.A. Krutesky highlights the following among the motives that can be found in teenagers:

- a teenager's interest in a subject;
- Desire to benefit the country;
- demonstrate personal ability;
- to observe family traditions;
- that he took the example of his friends and comrades;
- proximity of workplace and school to home;
- material security;
- motives such as the beauty of the school's appearance or the ease of settling in it. The

main methods of formation of educational motivation

Formation of intelligent, enlightened, humane, independent-thinking, inquisitive, entrepreneurial, innovative, proud of their nation and confident in the future young people who can meet the requirements of the time in order to achieve the great goals set for the members of the society today. the need arose. President Shavkat Miromonovich has the following thoughts: "The greatest wealth is intelligence and knowledge, the greatest inheritance is good education, and the greatest poverty is ignorance." Indeed, if we do not educate our children today, we cannot look forward to the future.

Motivation is an important factor that regulates human activity, behavior and activity. Because under various actions of a person there are reasons for these actions, their motivation. Therefore, the educational process is affected not only by learning-knowledge motives, but by all comprehensive motives with their sphere of influence. Teaching - encouraging and supporting the educational process. We need to educate a person who actively participates in the educational process, who can feel responsibility for his own views.

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